

A Plan Towards a European eDNA Digital Ecosystem: Activities and Outputs

SCAN ME

eDNAAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

eDNAAqua-Plan is a three-year initiative to pave the way for a more harmonised and interoperable landscape for aquatic eDNA data across Europe. Bringing together experts and stakeholders from diverse fields, the project will assess the current state of the aquatic eDNA data landscape and develop a forward-looking, efficient, and sustainable vision—anchored in **FAIR principles** and aligned with global standards.

Ultimately, eDNAAqua-Plan will deliver a **technical blueprint** for the future eDNA digital ecosystem, accompanied by an **implementation roadmap** designed in collaboration with key stakeholders. Our legacy will support future biodiversity monitoring programmes and contribute to the implementation of the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive**, the **Water Framework Directive**, and support the objectives of the **EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters**, the **European Green Deal** and the **European Ocean Pact**.

Discover more about eDNAAqua-Plan, explore our full range of resources, and engage with the growing **eDNA community!**

ednaquaplan.com

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18 project partners

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